

Studies on Hydrated Stannic Oxide : Part V : Selective Recovery of Phosphate from Basic Slag

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K_d values of phosphate, Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were studied on hydrated stannic oxide. Based on this a process of recovery of phosphate from basic slags of Indian Steel Plants is suggested with a recovery of over 95%.

HYDRATED stannic oxide acts as a cation as well as anion exchanger^{1,2}. Its anion exchange properties have been investigated extensively in our laboratory²⁻⁴. During the study it was observed that phosphate has high K_d -value at pH 2. This was made use of for a selective recovery of phosphate from basic slags of Indian Steel Plants.

Experimental

Reagents : All the reagents were of analytical grade.

Apparatus : ELICO pH meter model LI-10 (India) was used for pH measurement.

Spectromom-202 (Hungary) was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

Anion exchange column (i.d. 1.2 cm, length-3.0 cm) was used for column operation.

Preparation of hydrated stannic oxide (batch 2) :

As reported earlier². It was then dried at 300° for one hour before use. The exchanger is insoluble in 1(M) NaOH and 2(M) HClO₄.

Results and Discussion

Composition of Basic Slags :

The composition in percentage of basic slags of different Indian Steel Plants were determined⁵⁻⁷ : Bokaro Basic Slag, CaO (42.25), MgO(4.62), FeO (16.86), MnO(4.50), Al₂O₃(6.42), P₂O₅(2.24), SiO₂ (22.35); Burnpur Basic Slag, CaO(41.90), MgO (6.97), FeO(15.75), MnO(5.45), Al₂O₃(7.25), P₂O₅ (5.41), SiO₂(16.70); B.A.S. Basic Slag (31a)† CaO (45.00), MgO(7.44), FeO(5.65), MnO(5.01), Al₂O₃ (1.6), P₂O₅(13.3), SiO₂(14.6).

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Ion-Exchange capacity measurement :

The ion-exchange capacity of hydrated stannic oxide (OH⁻ form) was estimated by batch operation². One gram of hydrated stannic oxide was equilibrated with 100 ml of 1.9(M) NaNO₃ in 0.1M HNO₃ solution for 40 hours at room temperature. The amount of acid neutralised was estimated with standard sodium hydroxide solution. The anion exchange capacity was found to be 1.32 meq. (NO₃⁻)/gm of hydrated stannic oxide.

Distribution co-efficient (K_d) measurement :

The distribution co-efficient (K_d -values) of phosphate, Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Mn^{2+} at pH 2 (initial) were determined by equilibrating 100 ml of metal ions/phosphate solutions for 40 hours at room temperature with one gram of hydrated stannic oxide (OH⁻ form). The metal ions and phosphate concentration were kept at 4.5×10^{-4} (M). The metal ions present in the solution phase before and after shaking were estimated with standard disodium salt of EDTA⁸ solution and phosphate present in the solution phase before and after shaking was estimated spectrophotometrically⁹. The K_d -values were calculated as before⁸ given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION CO-EFFICIENTS OF THE IONS ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE AT (30 ± 2°C)

Anions/Cations	K_d -value
Phosphate	Total adsorption
Al ³⁺	0.2
Fe ³⁺	32.9
Mn ²⁺	1.1
Ca ²⁺	0.2
Mg ²⁺	0.9

Phosphate uptake by the different forms of exchanger :

Different forms (NO₃⁻, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻) of the

exchanger were prepared by shaking the exchanger (OH⁻ form) with 2(M) of corresponding sodium salt in 0.1(M) corresponding acid, then washed with deionised water and dried. Phosphate uptake by the different forms of exchanger at pH 2 (initial) was determined by following method: 0.5 g of different forms of exchanger were shaken with 100 ml of 5 × 10⁻³(M) phosphate solution in different bottles for 40 hours at room temperature. The phosphate in solution phase before and after shaking was determined spectrophotometrically⁶. The phosphate uptake has been calculated by the difference and tabulated in Table 2. Nitrate and chloride ions interfered during estimation of phosphate⁶ and manganese⁷ respectively. Hence sulphate form of exchanger was used in the latter part of the work. It is evident from the results in Table 2, that phosphate uptake by the exchanger is highest (15.1 mg/0.5 g exchanger) when the exchanger is in the OH⁻ form whereas phosphate uptake is least (12.2 mg/0.5 g exchanger) when the exchanger is in the NO₃⁻ form.

TABLE 2—PHOSPHATE UPTAKE BY THE DIFFERENT FORM OF HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE AT pH 2 (INITIAL)

Form of exchanger	Phosphate uptake (mg/0.5 g exchanger)
OH ⁻ form	15.1
NO ₃ ⁻ form	12.2
Cl ⁻ form	13.8
SO ₄ ²⁻ form	13.2

Interference study :

The interference due to NO₃⁻, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, Mn²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ on phosphate uptake by hydrated stannic oxide (OH⁻ form) at pH 2 (initial) were studied by equilibration as before. The results are presented graphically (Figs. 1 and 2).

It is evident from the results that SO₄²⁻ ion (bivalent) competes more strongly with the PO₄³⁻

Fig. 1. Interference of anions on phosphate uptake by hydrated tin dioxide

Fig. 2. Interference of metal ions on phosphate uptake by hydrated tin dioxide.

ion than Cl⁻ or NO₃⁻ ion. At low concentration of SO₄²⁻ ion, PO₄³⁻ ion is more selective than SO₄²⁻ ion by the exchanger under identical condition [K_{dSO₄²⁻} = 290 and K_{dPO₄³⁻} = Total adsorption].

The interference on phosphate uptake by the exchanger is slight due to presence of 10⁻⁴(M) any foreign cations in the solutions. When the concentration of Fe³⁺ is higher than 10⁻³(M) in solution phase, it affects the phosphate uptake considerably. However, this interference due to Fe³⁺ ion was removed by dilution. It was observed that when 100 ml of the mixture containing 5 × 10⁻³(M) PO₄³⁻ and 10⁻²(M) Fe³⁺ was diluted to 300 ml and the mixture was shaken with 0.5 g of the exchanger, the interference was considerably minimised. For large scale industrial application the amount of iron in the slag can be reduced by initial electromagnetic separation.

Column elution study :

Breakthrough capacity is more important for column operation. The breakthrough capacity of hydrated stannic oxide column was determined as follows: the column. (i.d. 1.2 cm, length 3.0 cm) was prepared with 5 gms of hydrated stannic oxide (OH⁻ form) of particle size 100-200 mesh. It was washed with dilute H₂SO₄ of appropriate strength before use. pH of the phosphate solutions (0.88 mg/ml) were adjusted with dilute H₂SO₄. The phosphate solutions were then passed through the column with a flow rate 0.8-1.0 ml/minute. It was observed that leakage of phosphate started at pH 2-4 after 10 ml of effluent which indicated that maximum 8.8 mg phosphate is adsorbed under that condition.

Elution studies of phosphate were carried out with 1.0(M) (NH₄)₂SO₄ in 1.0(M) H₂SO₄, 2.0(M)

$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ in 1.0(M) H_2SO_4 , 0.1(M) NH_4OH , 0.5(M) NH_4OH , 0.1(M) NaOH , 0.5(M) NaOH , 1.0(M) NaOH and 2.0(M) H_2SO_4 . Quantitative elution of phosphate was obtained either with 1.0(M) NaOH or 2.0(M) H_2SO_4 . Elution constant ($E=0.2285$) and bed distribution co-efficient ($D=\frac{1}{E}=4.376$) for 1.0(M) NaOH eluant was calculated as usual¹⁰.

Individual solutions of Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} at pH 2 (initial) were passed through the exchanger column. Fe^{3+} was partly adsorbed and then selectively eluted either with 35 ml of 2(M) HClO_4 or with 25 ml of 0.72(M) H_2SO_4 while phosphate remained adsorbed strongly by the hydrated stannic oxide. The phosphate was eluted quantitatively with 250 ml of aqueous 1.0(M) NaOH . The rate of elution was kept at 5-6 drops/minute.

The selective separation of phosphate from binary mixture with Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} (containing ~0.5 mg phosphate and ~0.5 mg metal ion in solution) have been achieved initially. Only in the case of Fe^{3+} - PO_4^{3-} mixture, Fe^{3+} was selectively eluted as above while phosphate remained adsorbed strongly by the exchanger.

On the basis of the above experimental results, a synthetic mixture of basic slag, similar in composition to Burnpur basic slag containing phosphate 0.1 mg/ml, was prepared. The pH of the solution was kept nearly at 1.7 (initial).

An aliquot of synthetic basic slag solution was added at the top of the exchanger column (sulphate form) and the effluent was collected. The column was washed with 35 ml 2(M) HClO_4 followed by 20 ml distilled water. The total effluent was tested for phosphate and found absent. The mixed effluent in duplicate runs was analysed and found that all metal ions including Fe^{3+} were present quantitatively. Adsorbed phosphate was then eluted with 250 ml of 1 (M) NaOH solution. The rate of elution was kept at 5-6 drops/minute. Phosphate was estimated spectrophotometrically⁹.

The above experiment was repeated with the Burnpur basic slag, B.A.S. basic slag (31a) and Bokaro basic slag. The slag solutions except Bokaro

slag were prepared in such a way that the concentration of phosphate in solution became 0.1 mg/ml. In the case of Bokaro slag solution, the phosphate concentration was adjusted at 0.05 mg/ml in order to lower down the interference of Fe^{3+} on the uptake of phosphate by hydrated stannic oxide. The pH of all the solutions were kept at 1.7 (initial). The phosphate recovery was fairly satisfactory and reproducible. The results are tabulated in Table 3.

TABLE 3 RECOVERY OF PHOSPHATE FROM BASIC SLAG

Slag's solution pH 1.7	PO_4^{3-} taken (mg)	PO_4^{3-} recovered (mg)	% of recovery
Synthetic	4.5	4.48	99.5
Burnpur	4.5	4.46	99.1
B.A.S. (31a)	5.0	4.9	98.00
Bokaro	3.2	3.12	97.5

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